

Vitamin D Induced Hypercalcemia In Myelodysplastic Syndrome: A Case of Uncommon But Reversible Cause

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ABSTRACT

Hypercalcemia is a common metabolic complication, most frequently associated with primary hyperparathyroidism and malignancy, while vitamin-D intoxication is an under-recognized but potentially reversible cause, particularly in patients with underlying comorbidities; a 63-year-old male with myelodysplastic syndrome presented with gastrointestinal symptoms and was found to have severe hypercalcemia with suppressed parathyroid hormone levels, with medication review revealing prolonged vitamin-D supplementation as the probable cause, and the patient was managed with cessation of vitamin-D, intravenous hydration, calcitonin, and zoledronic acid, resulting in normalization of serum calcium levels and clinical recovery, emphasizing the need for cautious use and regular monitoring of vitamin-D supplementation, especially in patients with comorbid conditions that predispose them to metabolic complications.

Keywords: Hypercalcemia; Vitamin-D toxicity; Myelodysplastic syndrome; Dietary supplements; Calcium homeostasis; Bisphosphonates; Calcitonin; Parathyroid hormone suppression..

INTRODUCTION

Calcium is a positively charged ion that is normally present in the blood at a level of about 2.1–2.6 mmol/L. However, only around 1% of the body's total calcium is found in the blood; most of it is stored in the bones. In the blood, nearly half of the calcium is bound to albumin and other ions, making it inactive and unable to take part in body functions. The other half circulates freely in an ionized, active form (about 1.1–1.3 mmol/L), which the body can use. The balance of calcium in the body is carefully regulated by the hormones, bones, digestive system, and kidneys working together. When this balance is disturbed, calcium levels can rise, leading to hypercalcemia, which means the blood calcium level goes above the normal upper limit of about 2.5–2.6 mmol/L (or 10–10.5 mg/dL, depending on the lab). Hypercalcemia is classified as mild, moderate, or severe (hypercalcemic crisis) based on how high the calcium level is.

Calcium levels are mainly controlled by three key hormones: parathyroid hormone (PTH), calcitonin, and Vitamin-D. In the kidneys, PTH and Vitamin-D help increase calcium reabsorption by activating specific calcium channels and binding proteins. Other hormones, such as thyroid hormones, growth hormone, and adrenal and sex steroids, also influence calcium levels in the body [1]. About 90% of cases of hypercalcemia are caused by hyperparathyroidism or cancer. About 20- 30% of cancer patients experience this problem at some stage of their illness. In cancer relate cases, nearly 80% are due to the action of PTH related peptide, while in the remaining cases it is due to the spreading of cancer to the bones. The remaining 10% of cases are from several different and less common causes. These include excess Vitamin-D, conditions where bones break down too quickly. Hypercalcemia due to bone breakdown occurs from excessive osteoclast-mediated bone resorption via RANK L (Receptor Activator of Nuclear Factor-κB Ligand) activation, leading to increased release of calcium into the bloodstream. Causes related to

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Vitamin-D include the following: Vitamin-D toxicity [2,3], Granulomatous disease (especially sarcoidosis [4]. High calcium can also occur as a side effect in people treated with synthetic parathyroid hormone for postmenopausal osteoporosis [5]. Milk alkali syndrome now often called calcium alkali syndrome, has become the third most common cause of hypercalcemia in hospitalized patients since 1990s [6,7]. The diagnosis of hypercalcemia in patients with haematological disorders is challenging, as it is frequently attributed to disease progression or malignancy-associated mechanisms. Vitamin- D intoxication remains an under-recognized and potentially reversible cause, underscoring the importance of thorough metabolic evaluation. This case report describes a rare presentation of severe hypercalcemia secondary to Vitamin-D intoxication in a patient with Myelodysplastic syndrome, highlighting the diagnostic approach, underlying pathophysiology, and management challenges. Awareness of this association is essential to ensure timely diagnosis and prevent avoidable morbidity.

CASE REPORT:

A 63-year-old Male patient was presented with diffuse abdominal pain, 3-4 episodes of vomiting, constipation along with abdominal distension and mild shortness of breath. On admission, the patient was conscious, oriented, and cooperative. He was afebrile, heart rate was 90beats/min, respiratory rate was 20 breaths/min, blood pressure was 120/70 mmHg. Random blood sugar level was 140mg/dl. His past medical history was significant for multiple comorbidities, including Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Hypertension, Myelodysplastic Syndrome with a TP53 mutation, and Coronary Artery Disease. The patient had a prior history of fundal gastric varices for which he underwent endoscopic cyanoacrylate glue injection. Patient was on medications for comorbid conditions, which include Carvedilol (3.125mg) for hypertension and variceal bleed prophylaxis and Voglibose in combination with Glimepride and Metformin (0.2mg+2mg+500mg) for diabetes. On routine evaluation, investigations showed elevated Vitamin D levels of 93ng/ml, elevated ionic calcium and serum calcium levels of 1.95mmol/liter and 12.4mg/dl respectively. On review, the patient had been receiving long-term vitamin D supplementation

at 1200 IU daily for the past one year, suggesting supplement-induced hypercalcemia as the most probable cause. Parathyroid hormone levels were low at 6 pg/mL, effectively ruling out PTH-dependent hypercalcemia. Serum electrolytes were within normal limits: sodium-136mEq/L, potassium-4.1mEq/L, chlorides-86mEq/L, phosphate-3.7mg/dl, magnesium-1.9mEq/L. Mild renal impairment was observed with blood urea 37mg/dl, serum creatinine 1.54mg/dl and creatinine clearance 48ml/min. Hemogram showed evidence of cytopenia which is likely secondary to patient's underlying myelodysplastic syndrome with hemoglobin at 5.2g/dl, platelet count at $150 \times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$, total leucocyte count at $3.66 \times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$. Iron panel was performed to assess the disease progression of Myelodysplastic syndrome revealing elevated serum ferritin 500ng/ml, normal serum iron levels 121 mcg/dl, low Total Iron Binding Capacity (TIBC) 111mcg/dl. All of which concluded anemia of chronic disease without iron deficiency. These findings are consistent with anemia of chronic disease (MDS) rather than iron deficiency. Liver function tests were normal except for a reduced albumin level of 2.0 g/dL. Coagulation profile revealed normal APTT, prolonged prothrombin time (PT) at 19.27 seconds, and normal INR at 1.37. The ESR was markedly elevated at 140 mm/hr, while the CRP was mildly raised at 31 mg/dL. NT-Pro BNP was elevated with 3282pg/ml indicating significant myocardial stress. Bone Mineral Density score was low with -2.4 indicating osteopenia. Upper GI endoscopy revealed Esophageal varices, Fundal Varices, mild PHG (Portal hypertensive gastropathy). 2D echo showed LVEF-60%, mild aortic regurgitation, severe aortic stenosis, CT abdomen confirmed moderate ascites and right mild pleural effusion accompanied by bilateral haziness was noted on chest X-ray. In this case, the patient was given IV fluids (0.9% NS) and was started on Calcitonin IV (200IU) for hypercalcemia. Albumin (20%) 20gms was given to correct hypoalbuminemia. Lactulose syrup PO(30 ml) was prescribed to relieve constipation. After adequate hydration was achieved, the patient was initiated on Furosemide (20mg) to maintain urine output and avoid volume overload, given the background of non-oliguric AKI. Additionally, he was initiated on Rifaximin PO (550mg) and Lactitol monohydrate PO (20ml) as prophylaxis against hepatic

encephalopathy, given his underlying chronic liver disease. He received four units of PRBCs during his present hospital admission for severe anemia, after which his hemoglobin increased to 8.2g/dl. Glycemic control was achieved using a basal-bolus regimen comprising insulin glulisine administered three times daily prior to meals and insulin glargine administered once daily at night, with doses adjusted based on serial blood glucose monitoring. Ascitic tapping was done as CT abdomen showed ascites. After five days of calcitonin therapy, the patient's serum calcium decreased to 10.6 mg/dL, prompting discontinuation of the drug. Subsequently, calcium levels rose to 10.8 mg/dL, and calcitonin was reinitiated at a reduced dose. Carvedilol was continued as mentioned in medication reconciliation.

During the hospital course, the patient developed low-grade fevers with chills and generalized body aches, managed with Paracetamol. One dose of Hydrocortisone IV (10mg) was given as chills

persisted. Additionally, hypokalemia (serum potassium 3.2 mEq/L) was noted and corrected with Potassium chloride (40 mEq in 300 mL normal saline over 4hours IV). Darbeoetin alfa (500 mcg SC, STAT) was administered for anemia, with a plan to continue maintenance dose of 100 mcg subcutaneously once weekly. Bisphosphonate (Zoledronic acid 4mg in 100ml NS STAT IV infusion) was administered to achieve sustained control of serum calcium levels.

The patient recovered and was discharged after 15 days of hospital stay, with normalization of calcium levels and stabilization of hemoglobin. [Table 1] However, platelet and WBC counts remained slightly low, for which Filgrastim 300 mcg subcutaneously was planned following review in the outpatient department. The discharge medications included: Lactulose (30ml OD), Carvedilol (3.125mg BD), Voglibose with Metformin and Glimepride (0.2+500+2mg TID) and Rifaximin (550mg BD).

Table 1: Laboratory parameters during hospital stay

Labs	D1	D3	D7	D9	D11	D13
Calcium(mg/dl)	12.4	12.7	12.2	10.6	10.8	9.9
Hemoglobin(g/dl)	5.2	5.3	5.9	6.2	7.2	8.2
TLC (X 10 ³ /mm ³)	3.66	4.34	3.96	3.61	3.4	2.7
Platelets (X 10 ³ /mm ³)	150	150	100	89	58	47

Values represent laboratory measurements obtained during hospitalization following treatment for Vitamin D-induced hypercalcemia.

DISCUSSION:

Vitamin-D plays an essential role in regulating calcium balance through its actions on the gastrointestinal tract, bone, and kidneys [8]. Beyond its skeletal functions, it exerts pleiotropic effects in cancer, cardiovascular diseases, and autoimmune diseases. The suggested health benefits, combined with the high global prevalence of Vitamin-D deficiency, led to a widespread rise in the use of Vitamin-D supplements. However, Vitamin-D supplementation is not without risk; toxicity represents a significant adverse event, with several reports documenting intoxication even after short-term use. Long-term safety data remain limited, with only a small number of reports describing prolonged

high-dose exposure, demonstrating considerable heterogeneity in individual responses to sustained supraphysiologic Vitamin-D levels [9-11]. The Food and Nutrition Board (FNB) at the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine has established recommended dietary allowances and adequate intakes for vitamin D. These values range from 15 to 20 mcg (600–800 IU) per day for adults and from 10 to 15 mcg (400– 600 IU) per day for infants, children, and adolescents, depending on age. Vitamin-D toxicity can cause hypercalcemia, hypercalciuria, and high serum 25(OH)D concentrations; in extreme cases, it may lead to renal failure, calcification of soft tissues, cardiac arrhythmias, and death. Vitamin D toxicity is almost always a result of excessive intakes of vitamin D through supplements. The FNB established upper limits for Vitamin-D which emphasizes that although daily doses below 250 mcg (10,000 IU) rarely cause acute toxicity, sustained supplementation at doses

below this limit may still be detrimental to health. The FNB recommended avoiding serum 25(OH) Vitamin-D levels above approximately 125 to 150 nmol/L (50–60 ng/mL), and it found that even lower serum levels (approximately 75–120 nmol/L [30–48 ng/mL]) are associated with increase in rates of all-cause mortality, risk of cancer at some sites (e.g., pancreas), risk of cardiovascular events, and number of falls and fractures among older adults^[12].

Myelodysplastic syndromes are clonal hematopoietic stem cell disorders that primarily affect older adults and arise through a multistep pathogenic process driven by cytogenetic abnormalities, gene mutations, or a combination of both. These syndromes are marked by ineffective hematopoiesis resulting in peripheral blood cytopenias and, in approximately one-third of patients, progression to acute myeloid leukemia (AML)^[13]. Patients with MDS frequently experience chronic fatigue, anorexia, and reduced nutritional status, for which clinicians prescribe Vitamin-D supplements as part of routine supportive care. In addition, MDS-related bone marrow dysfunction can indirectly influence calcium and phosphate homeostasis, potentially modifying the patient's response to exogenous Vitamin-D. Many patients with MDS also have coexisting renal insufficiency which may be age-related or secondary to comorbidities, which may impair the clearance of 25(OH) Vitamin-D and reduce the ability to excrete excess calcium, thereby exacerbating the risk of hypercalcemia^[14]. Furthermore, reduced mobility and periods of hospitalization, which are common in MDS, can contribute to bone resorption, predisposing these patients to more severe manifestations of Vitamin-D toxicity^[15]. The goals of treating hypercalcemia include increased elimination from the extracellular fluid, reduced gastrointestinal absorption, and decreased bone resorption. Management of hypercalcemia begins with aggressive IV 0.9% saline hydration to correct volume depletion and restore urine output. Associated electrolyte disturbances should be corrected to prevent further complications. Calcitonin provides rapid but short-term calcium reduction. Bisphosphonates (especially Zoledronic acid) offer more sustained control but take 2–3 days to act^[16]. Glucocorticoids (e.g., Prednisone 20–40 mg/day) are effective for hypercalcemia related to lymphoma or

granulomatous disease by suppressing calcitriol production.

Recent advances in the management of hypercalcemia focus on a pathophysiology-based and organ-specific approach^[17]. Denosumab has emerged as an effective alternative to bisphosphonates, particularly in patients with renal impairment or refractory hypercalcemia.^[17,18] Recognition of calcitonin tachyphylaxis has shifted practice towards early initiation of longer-acting antiresorptive agents^[19]. In Vitamin-D mediated hypercalcemia, glucocorticoids remain the mainstay of treatment, while Ketoconazole can be used as a potential steroid-sparing option, as it inhibits 1- α -hydroxylase and thereby reduces the production of active Vitamin-D (calcitriol), however, its use is limited by hepatotoxicity^[20,21]. Individualized treatment strategies are recommended in patients with coexisting renal, hepatic, and hematologic disorders^[17,22].

PATIENT EDUCATION

Patients should avoid unsupervised use of over-the-counter supplements, particularly vitamin D and calcium preparations. Regular follow-up and biochemical monitoring are essential, and symptoms such as nausea, constipation, weakness, or confusion should prompt immediate medical evaluation.

CHALLENGES:

Diagnostic Challenges:

1. Attributing hypercalcemia to Vitamin-D: Hypercalcemia in patients with MDS, chronic kidney disease, and chronic liver disease can have multiple etiologies (malignancy-related, medication-induced, or endocrine), making it challenging to detect Vitamin-D as the primary cause.
2. Overlap of symptoms: Nonspecific symptoms such as abdominal pain, vomiting, and malaise could be due to hypercalcemia, underlying liver disease, infection, or cardiac strain.

Therapeutic Challenges:

1. Balancing hydration and renal function: The patient had mild renal impairment, requiring

careful IV fluid administration to correct hypercalcemia without causing volume overload.

2. Management of comorbidities: Coexisting anaemia, cytopenia's, chronic liver disease, and cardiac disease complicated therapy choices.
3. Calcitonin tachyphylaxis: Calcium rebounded after initial therapy, requiring careful monitoring and re-initiation at a lower dose.

ROLE OF PHARMACIST IN PREVENTING SUPPLEMENT OVERUSE:

Dietary supplements can be useful and safe when used appropriately, but inappropriate use or overuse through self-prescribing may cause adverse effects, interfere with other medications, and negatively impact public health. Pharmacists play a vital role in promoting the safe and rational use of these supplements by counselling patients, educating them about potential drug-supplement interactions, consequences of overuse and guiding proper dosing. Pharmacists, with their expertise in medications and nutrition and their easy accessibility, can support healthcare providers by identifying high-risk patients and providing individualized recommendations. Additionally, pharmacists contribute to developing policies and guidelines to regulate supplement use across specific populations such as children, pregnant women, and patients with chronic conditions. By combining knowledge of pharmacology, nutrition, and public health, pharmacists serve as an essential resource for preventing overuse and optimizing the safe use of dietary supplements.

CONCLUSION:

This case represents a unique instance of hypercalcemia secondary to Vitamin-D intoxication in a patient with Myelodysplastic syndrome (MDS), a scenario rarely reported in the literature. It underscores that even moderate doses of Vitamin-D (1200IU), when administered long-term, can precipitate significant hypercalcemia, particularly in patients with comorbidities that alter calcium and Vitamin-D metabolism. Early recognition and prompt management including discontinuation of Vitamin-D supplementation, hydration, Calcitonin, Bisphosphonates, and treatment of underlying conditions, can prevent complications and improve outcomes.

Clinicians should exercise caution with supplementation and closely monitor biochemical parameters, as serum 25(OH) Vitamin-D levels in the range of 70–100 ng/mL may be sufficient to induce toxicity in susceptible individuals. Furthermore, hypercalcemia with suppressed PTH should prompt suspicion for Vitamin-D toxicity, highlighting the need for vigilance in hematologic disorders. This case offers significant insight into an under-recognized clinical risk and underscores the critical need for heightened awareness and systematic reporting of supplement overuse to mitigate future adverse outcomes.

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